

PROBLEMS OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF NATIONAL PHILOSOPHY IN THE CURRENT PERIOD

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Annotation: Philosophy, the father of science, is a way of knowing the world around. His place in our lives is incalculable. The article deals with the problems of the development of Russian philosophy in modern times.

Key words: national philosophy, technique, philosophical problems, general patterns, methodology, philosophical research, philosophical reflection.

Today, in the age of speeds and high technologies, philosophy is needed, is it not outdated? Does certain knowledge not compress philosophy in the context of continuous information flow and chronic time scarcity? Such questions are absolutely relevant, but the answer to them is given by life itself, which puts in front of a person of the present time a large number, including completely new philosophical problems that have never existed before. The world community opposed the beginning of the 3rd millennium, with an increasingly thoughtful understanding of the state of the biosphere and its own responsibility for the continuation of life on Earth. For this reason, the issues of the harmonious development of Man, the establishment of human, good-neighborly relations between people, peoples, as well as between society and nature, are gaining priority in philosophical research, along with long-standing philosophical topics. In this regard, philosophers first express a strong concern about the state and level of development of education on Earth. According to many philosophers, most of the current problems lie in Zamiri precisely the unsatisfactory education and the absence of the necessary level of Education. Philosophy should also play a role in solving these problems.

Philosophy as a way of understanding the world. Today, not only some peoples, but the entire world community are especially in need of philosophy, a philosophical understanding of its place and function in life. Philosophy is inextricably linked with real life and is always focused on realizing the most important problems of the human being. It is for this reason that the important problem of the present era is globalization and its philosophical realization as a completely new subject in philosophy. Another topic that deserves special attention when discussing the subject and problems of philosophy is the role and significance of philosophy in educating and maturing a person as a person.

As philosophers of the present time continue to work on solving such problems, - what is philosophy? Who and why is he needed? - What is the function of philosophy?,- How to study philosophy, from what age and for what purpose? at a glance at the tribe, they are putting the issues that have already paid for their solution on the agenda again. The World Congresses, about which there are many and exhaustively spoken World Congresses, confirm that the only approach in the world to the subject of philosophy, as well as to whether or not he is able to consistently influence social development, in what way he can do it, if he is able,

does not exist as before. Such a variety of opinions, as noted above, is determined by the peculiarity of philosophy, that is, it can exist only where there is a pluralism of thoughts, the possibility of different kinds of thinking. Hegel's opinion on this is firm: "every philosophical system has existed and continues to exist in a necessary way: so none of them has been lost, all has been preserved as moments of one Integrity [1, 40]".

This drawback of philosophy, which does not allow it to become a holistic doctrine and rely on the unity of language, general laws and methodology, at the same time becomes its advantage, when it works with complex systems that require the solution of interdisciplinary complex problems. The following are currently the most important interdisciplinary complex problems for humanity: ensuring sustainable socio-economic development; problems of Ecology; globalization of all aspects of society's life. It is of particular importance to realize these problems from a philosophical point of view. In contrast to scientific approaches, the philosophical approach to the problem is characterized by greater freedom in the interpretation of evidence, more lenient requirements for the proof of the rules being put forward, giving definitions based on observation, the right to subjective assessment, and so on. It may also seem that such research is of little importance at first glance. But in practice this is not the case.

First of all, philosophical research is carried out in the field of rational knowledge, which, due to the inability to verify (verify) or reject (falsify) the results obtained in science, has not achieved the necessary effect or turned out to be completely helpless. Humanity has no other methods of rational cognition than this.

Second, philosophical reflection broadens the horizon of vision of the problem, offering novel, idiosyncratic approaches to its research, including promoting such approaches to science.

After all, science, relying on clear definitions and reliable evidence, cannot allow such freedoms in its thoughts and conclusions. However, philosophical thought loses its uniqueness without a free approach to reasoning and assessments. "The real conflict of philosophy lies in the anarchism of one and only philosophical systems, the essence of which is that the abundance of philosophical views and their unparalleled mutual struggle form two sides of one whole [2, 210]".

Still, pluralism is considered the norm in philosophy, and in each individual brain it is necessary to come to monism, that is, an ordered, holistic and relatively conflict-free system of views, how to master philosophy, what lessons can be taught from it?

Most philosophers all over the world are primarily interested in the same issue. In particular, relying on the experience of Socrates, Seneca and other thinkers of the past: philosophy should not teach to remember facts, but develop the ability to reason and answer questions. The lessons from philosophy are that a person learns to think independently and listen to his own mind, without resorting to the opinion of thinkers on each issue. For this reason, the task of philosophy is to teach a person to communicate, to achieve that he tries to reach the bottom of reality, and not to show the importance of his personality. This, in turn, implies that all people deserve to be listened to by those around them.

This is a further confirmation of the idea that highly paid words cannot be studied as a science of philosophy, assimilating it as a certain sum of knowledge, ready-made rules and definitions. When teaching a person, it is necessary to choose the path of the recorder – to teach him not "what to see", but "where and how to look." It is clear in itself that this task cannot be solved

without a creative approach, without the curiosity and aspiration of the student and teacher, while philosophy disappears in its pure form, “sucks into the air”, ultimately leaving behind a fangina that someone describes, someone –must pass, learn and, moreover, complete the exam. In other words, even at the time of teaching and mastering philosophy, creativity should definitely lie.

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